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Effects of a Shintergy-sinchronized brain over a laser beam, chronometers and a scale weight: a Possible Fractal Structure of Consciousness.

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Strong correlations are found between brain activity of a subject performing Shintergy-like synchronization under controlled conditions, and measurements made with a 100mW, 532nm laser, an arduino weight scale, and a pair of arduino chronometers distanced 1.5-3m from each other. Mathematical fractal techniques were applied to the raw data, showing a strong correlation of fractality and the Shintergy-synchronization activities. Consciousness is theorized as a multifractal (a nest of percolating networks, with local manifestations of a particular hierarchy of consciousness), having local collapses of gravitational singularities, and some evidence of it was found using concepts from general relativity and Bose-Einstein condensates.

KEYWORDS

Fractal consciousness, *Shintergy*, synchronization, quantum non-locality, Dark matter, altered states of consciousness, gravitational anomalies, general relativity, Bose-Einstein condensates, percolating hierarchies

* Equally contributing authors.

1 | INTRODUCTION

"[...] it is inherent in human consciousness to notice some facts about the things one is doing" [1].

Possibly one of the earliest mention of the concept of consciousness is related with Samyutta Nikaya 22.79 [2]: "And why do you call it 'consciousness'? Because it cognizes, thus it is called consciousness. What does it cognize? It cognizes what is sour, bitter, pungent, sweet, alkaline, non-alkaline, salty, & unsalty. Because it cognizes, it is called consciousness."

In the Upanishads [3] consciousness is not described in terms of what it is, but rather on what the states of it are, namely,

1. The waking state (bahish-prajnya)
2. The dreaming mind (antah-prajnya)
3. Deep sleep (susupti),
4. Pure consciousness (Turiya),

Intelligence has been related, if not used equivalently, to consciousness [1], and precisely because it is difficult to describe in operational terms what consciousness is, consciousness has been related to self-awareness, cognition and similar concepts [4], including the problem of free will [5].

On the side of physics there has been some attempts to show that consciousness (and related concepts) is a emergent property of a self-organized biological system [6] or any system, given a cumulative underlying logical recursivity [1].

Certainly one aspect of consciousness is the question concerning of "action at a distance", which at the very least has been useful to further research of fundamental physics [7]. Action at a distance, as has been used in physics, has also been suggested in context of so-called "quantum mysticism" [8], without giving much (if at all) operational foundations to work with.

In this work it is presented an operational definition of consciousness, based on the assumptions made by current knowledge of physiology of consciousness, quantum mechanics and relativity, which is then put to test experimentally, and the results ultimately related with the structure of the universe at large, through the concept of dark matter, exhibiting that consciousness and its varied manifestations, herein defined, must be pervasive at all scales, and all directions of space-time. Dark matter and dark energy have had attempts of explanations using different kinds of assumptions [9], including the possible omission of N-body effects [10]. As it will be seen, the experimental results rather point towards the collapse of a bosonic field, which create both the curvature of space-time and what consciousness itself, at least in the way that is herein defined.

With all the above and under an objective and critical focus, this research emerges with the precise question: *Can the Shintergy synchronization be observed and what would be its implications as an interaction, with clear effects on the light of a laser beam, gravity expressed as a change in the measures of a weight scale, and thus possibly some alteration of space-time?*

2 | QUANTUM FIELD THEORY AND THE FRACTAL CONSCIOUSNESS CONJECTURE

The idea of describing space-time and quantum effects through a fractal structure has been explored in several works [11, 12], and because consciousness has emerged or is present in this universe, it was conjectured in this work that it also could have a fractal structure.

The whole process involving the brain engagement with its environment has been referred to as the “dialog” between the brain and its Double (the environment is formally described by the “doubled” degrees of freedom, expressing at the same time the environment and the brain image. Consciousness has been proposed to be rooted in such a permanent dialog between the subject and its Double [13], and because this dialog can become self-referential, thus a recursive structure arises, and recursivity is a necessary and sufficient condition for a fractals to manifest into existence [14, 15].

More complex behavior can found when it is considered that fractals can be nested, and described as hierarchy of percolating networks, such as the models of turbulence [16].

2.1 | Definitions

The emergence of the simultaneous coherent cooperativity among neurons is exactly what the dissipative model of QUantum Field Theory predicts [17]; brain is a dissipative system coupled with the external world [18].

Under a convenient choice of the q-deformation parameter and by a suitable restriction to real α , coherent states exhibit fractal properties in the q-deformed space of the entire analytical functions.

Quantum entanglement is a label for the observed physical phenomenon that occurs when a pair or group of particles is generated, interact, or share spatial proximity in a way such that the quantum state of each particle of the pair or group cannot be described independently of the state of the others, even when the particles are separated by a large distance [19]. In his seminal paper [20], Bell departs from the same two assumptions as did the Einstein-Podolsky-Rossen paradox stated in 1935, namely

- i) reality (that microscopic objects have real properties determining the outcomes of quantum mechanical measurements)
- ii) locality (that reality in one location is not influenced by measurements performed simultaneously at a distant location)

Bell was able to derive from those two assumptions an important result, namely Bell's inequality. The theoretical (and later experimental) violation of this inequality implies that at least one of the two assumptions must be false. The results hereby presented challenge locality, both in time and space.

Let A_k be the bosonic operator of k degrees of freedom of the field. Let N_A a non-negative integer. at time $t_0 = 0$ we have infinitely many memory states (referentials), each one corresponding to a different number of N_{A_k} of A_k modes, for all k . Let $\dim_{Haus}(X)$ be the Hausdorff dimension of (X) and $\dim_{Leb}(X)$ be the embedding, Lebesgue dimension (for the mathematical definition of a fractal, [15] of *consciousness* X). Let G be the gravitational constant, M is the mass attained by a given X , and c the speed of light in vacuum [21].

2.2 | Fractal Consciousness Conjecture

Theorem 1 If $\lim_{k \rightarrow I} \cup_k \mathcal{N}_{A_k} = X$ such that $\dim_{Haus}(X) > \dim_{Leb}(X) \implies X = R < r_s$ where $r_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2}$ is the Schwarzschild radius, equivalent to a gravitational singularity. X is the definition of consciousness. Moreover, consciousness is a singularity in the probabilistic sense of a percolation system: given the occupation probability p , when $p = p_c$, and which would also depends on the size of the lattice L , but

$$P_\infty(p) = \lim_{L \rightarrow \infty} P_L(p)$$

also, at the percolation probability the probability that a given memory state is occupied at random, would belong to the maximal cluster (the whole universe), increases abruptly. In fact for $p > p_c$ and $p \sim p_c$ $P_\infty(p)$ is given by a power law

$$P_\infty(p) \propto (p - p_c)^\beta$$

, where β is a non-integer exponent.

The percolating network can be composed of a hierarchy of scales, such that the energy flow can be described as

$$V_{\lambda_n} = \left(\frac{\lambda}{\lambda_n} \right)^{M-1}, \quad \lambda_n \in \{\lambda_0 \ll \lambda_1 \ll \lambda_2 \dots\}$$

Where λ is a given embedding scale, λ_n is a nested scale, and M is a varying exponent parameter.

In other words, there is consciousness in that quantum dissipative system, which in simpler terms can be stated that

consciousness is the concatenation of references that when reaching a fractal condition collapse into singularity. The object concatenated are referentials (memory states), which reach a fractal condition and in turn collapse (coalesce) into a form of gravitational singularity.

Moreover, since a fractal can be described by power laws [14], and since many systems at their percolating threshold (a mathematical singularity, [14] do show a power law description [14], then it is possible to state a coherence and a link between a local (individual) consciousness with a global, non-localized one, spanning the whole universe. Such idea can be supported, for example with the findings of those like Fred Hoyle's concerning the discrepancy between a thermodynamic equilibrium which allows the nucleosynthesis of Iron [22] as opposed to that giving rise to the elements leading to those permitting life [23]. Awareness, thus, "it is not only the result of supposed computational activity of neuronal networks, but the integration of information from multiple reference frames across the entanglement network of spacetime." [24]. Moreover, a power-law distribution has been documented concerning the size distribution of interstellar, ultraviolet-blocking-light dust, which also matches the size distribution of spore-forming bacteria [25]. Finally, the existence of dark matter, departing from the assumption that the temperature fluctuations at the beginning of the universe were adiabatic do require a power law spectrum, non-baryonic cold dark matter, and quite probably the existence of bosonic fields [9]. Dark energy and dark matter manifest gravitationally, and is observable in structures like spiral galaxies [26]. The idea that a percolating network of singularities, has been stated in other works as worhole network [27]. In this work it is considered an alternative perspective, coherent with the experimental results, that solve the apparent controversy about the gravitational effects presumably caused by dark energy-matter [28]. The nested percolating networks suggested in conjecture 1, is based on the hierarchy of energy flows of models turbulence [16], and thus it is possible to describe hierarchies of consciousness.

3 | METHODOLOGY

3.1 | Experimental set-up for the physical measurements

The whole strategy of the physical measurements while on Shyntergy-synchronization is driven by the idea of quantum non-locality [20], both in time and space, so, three ways of measuring anomalies were chosen, namely, a laser, a weight scale, and two chronometers. All the devices used Arduino electronics and the Arduino program compiler [29].

In the following sections the design and construction of the equipment is going to be briefly described.

3.1.1 | Laser

A 100mW, 532nm laser, activated in continuous mode, was fixed on the extreme of a mounting that allow fine-tune of the supporting legs through screws. At the other side it was fixed a photocell (as a laser beam profiler) which registered any variation of brilliancy from the laser, rendering low numbers for high brilliancy, and bigger numbers for any increase of darkness. Between the laser beam and the said photocell, a focusing device was fixed, which consist of a hollow tube with a small perforation on one side, so that the laser beam arrives mostly within the diameter of the photocell (Fig.2).

The photocell is connected to an Arduino circuit, which in turn is connected to a computer (see paragraphs below for detailed explanation), where an Arduino program may be started to begin the registration of the measurements, until the Arduino plaque is disconnected, to allow the manual transcription of the collected measurements towards a spreadsheet. The strategy was that if the Shintergy synchronization could have any influence whatsoever, this would be registered as variations of the brilliancy. However, after the first experiments were made, it was clear that further devices were needed, to attempt to assert the nature of the phenomenon that made the brilliancy change. It is known that loss of received brilliancy would imply a loss of photons, which in turn usually can be ascribed to optical phenomena [30].

Under the development of the proper equipment for the laser experiment, the following principal points were taken into consideration (Fig.1):

Body Frame

With the help of a CAD software (Siemens NX 12) a model of the 1/2 inch galvanised pipe frame was design in such a way to hold the laser, filter the incoming beam of light and support the photoelectric resistor. The principal idea for which galvanised pipe was used as material for the construction of the system it is the great work versatility and stiffness of the material. These not only allowed the system to have a strong hold of the equipment but at the same time gives the possibility of adjustment on an irregular surface, this thanks to the pipe threading on the entire design (Fig.2).

Electronics

The integration of the electronics systems for the data acquisition was based on four main components which are

- Arduino
- Laser
- Resistor

FIGURE 1 Design mind-map.

- Photo-Resistor

Using a common resistance and photo-resistor, a voltage divider was created (Fig.3a). Based upon this electric principle, it was possible for the Arduino to read the analog signal values coming from the photo-resistor and convert them into digital ones able to be analyzed into a computer connected to the Arduino's serial port (Fig.3b). These values range from 0 to 1023 accordingly to the range voltage from 0 to 5 volts coming out from the photo-resistor (Fig.3).

It is important to note that the impedance of the photo resistor increases as the photon intensity decreases. This can be expressed with the following mathematical expression

$$I_p \propto \frac{1}{R} \quad (1)$$

FIGURE 2 Body frame.

(a) Voltage divider.

(b) Laser circuit diagram.

FIGURE 3 Circuitry for laser detection.

By Ohms Law, we can say that $V \propto R$; therefore

$$I_p \propto \frac{1}{V_{out}} \tag{2}$$

This design implication has a deep meaning in the test result, as can be seen by the above equations, the Arduino analog input registers high values as the photo-resistor register losses in photon intensity. The voltage across the

photo-resistor can be easily obtained with the next equation below

$$V_{\text{out}} = \frac{R_2}{R_1 + R_2} V_{\text{in}} \quad (3)$$

Programming

Two different sets of programming codes were designed, one was made on the Arduino programming language and the other on Excel Macros. These two codes were planned to work together in such a way that Arduino would collect the data from the photo-resistor and then transfer that information to an Excel spreadsheet. This was planned to analyze the data in a cleaner and easier way.

Weight Sensor and Chronometers

During the following experiments, three more components were added to the original system idea. These were

- 2 Electronic Chronometers
- 1 weight Sensor

These electronic components were included to detect time delay and gravitational anomalies near the testing equipment. It is important to note that these implementations to the system were conducted by an external third-party team which developed the electronic integration and programming independently of the laser test equipment (see the acknowledgments). Some details about them are discussed in the following paragraphs.

3.1.2 | Weight Scale

An Arduino weight scale was used for all the experiments. In some of the experiments no weight was used, while others used always the same three coins, weighing 12 grams altogether. As in the case of the laser, measurements were collected and transcribed from the Arduino program. The strategy was to collect data from which it could be inferred if the loss of brilliancy in the laser is connected to a temporal gravitational anomaly, much the same as would a gravitational singularity would do [31].

3.1.3 | Chronometers

A pair of Arduino chronometers distanced 1.5-3m from each other were set up. These set up comes from the idea of general relativity, where a clock near a gravitational singularity should work slower than a distant clock [31].

3.2 | The synchronization technique

Shintergy is a paradigm, a model and a methodology of human neuro-engineering and high performance, with 25 years of development in clinical and field research by the psychologist José Luis Bueno since 1995 in different environments and populations.

The brain-mind *Shintergy*-synchronization (henceforth referred to just as *Shintergy*) is focused in a complex range of perception and its interaction with the different levels of density, of what is now understood to be the quantum vacuum and the quantum field, through a simultaneous perception similar to contemplation [32] and that goes much

further that conventional meditative states [32] with a single focusing point (unipunctual).

Shintergy has emerged as a *synergy* from the following elements:

1. Jacobo Grinberg's Sintergic theory [33], received in collaboration and researched with Dr. Jacobo Grinberg
2. The Fracto-Holographic theory of Nassim Haramein and its approach about vacuum fluctuations with the spherical unit of vacuum. [12, 27]
3. The psycho-corporal perspective of sofrology from Alfonso Caycedo and David Parra. [34]
4. The psycho-corporal integration of high performance exercises about perception, taken from ancient cultures, namely, Mexican, Chinese, Tibetan, African and Hindu.
5. The SHIN model integrated by Jose Luis Bueno (one of the authors) derived from Yan Xin Qigong [35], focused on the individual and collective learning and development of potential.
6. The systemic perspective and the paradigm of medicine and traditional culture from China and Mexico.
7. The methodology, practice and activations from 20 years of brain training with teachers from Dzogchen of Tibetan Yungdrung Bon and other Tibetan Dzogchen teachers. [36]
8. The practice and perspective of Hindu Advaita. [37]
9. The integral perspective of clinical psychology and a unified vision of the main five currents of psychology (psychoanalysis, cognitive-behavioral, humanist, transpersonal and Neuro Psychology, as well as Biofeedback y Neurofeedback)
10. A holistic integrating perspective of alternative medicines, namely, resonance with human consciousness.
11. The integration of neurosciences, quantum physics, mathematics, psychology, psychoneuroimmunology, and complexity science at large. [38]
12. Theory of outcome mapping.[39]

In this way, the result is a methodology and a way of practicing brain synchronization, Shintergy style, as an interaction with the different levels of density of vacuum (understood both as the quantum field theory vacuum, and the vacuum of mystic contemplation in this context), focused for high performance both mental and physical.

For short, the combination and training in all the above will be called "Shintergy synchronization". It is a pluripunctual synchronization model (perception over several simultaneous targets) with zero interaction, i.e., there is no actual will of transformation of the self-reality, as it is the case when proprioceptive awareness allows animals to move as desired, with a separation between external stimuli and a reaction, or between planning and executing: it is intended to enter a state where no separation exists between the outward and inward reality, beyond perceived and/or remembered references of time and space. Paradoxically, such state is acquired through attempting to activate all the points of perception of the subject: internal (interoceptors), external (exteroceptors), and of the self (proprioceptors). Neurologically one of the observed phenomena (see section 3.3) is the switching off of the Default Mode Network which is the neurological network in charge of the self-identity of a person (who am I, where am I, what date is it) [40]. This event creates a paradoxical phenomenon: the subject experiences both a sort of self-dissolution, and yet individuality is preserved.

To fix ideas around testing quantum non-locality concerning consciousness, the Shintergy synchronization was measured when the subject, before starting, integrated a feeling of the desire for sending consciousness in a given direction of time and space. Such desire disappears altogether once actually in the mind state which is the result of applying Shintergy. The directions in time and space were labeled as follows:

1. Black: baseline. Measurement without the influence of the contemplating subject in Shintergy synchronization.
2. Yellow: present time, and physical proximity to physical measurements (in visual range).
3. Red: present time, at a distance (distant several or even thousands of kilometers).
4. Green: past time (Shintergy synchronization after the physical measurements, meaning at attempt to influence the past), at a distance.
5. Blue: future time (attempting to influence the future), at a distance.

In all the graphics of the raw data (without further processing), the above mentioned coloring was used. Fig.4 shows the arrows of time for each type of synchronization

FIGURE 4 The arrows of time for each type of synchronization. The measurements are done on a given day, and a choice is made which measurements are meant to be part of a Shintergy synchronization from the past (Future at a distance, or blue type); from the present (either at a distance -red type- or in spatial proximity -yellow type-); and from the future (which is past at a distance -green type-)

3.3 | Neurological measurements

In this report we are comparing each separated task against the same international database contained in Neuroguide [41]. The neurological measurements were analyzed with the software Z-Builder [41], and the laboratory results refer to the standard ten-twenty nomenclature for the electrodes in the head of the subject[42].

3.4 | Data postprocessing

All data postprocessing was performed with the help of the Wolfram's Mathematica, v.10.

3.4.1 | Direct data plot

The data was taken and plotted directly, so that all graphics show a progressive numbering related with the time stamp of that individual measurement, which in turn, depending on the device, had different sampling rate. On the y axis it is shown the amount of each individual measurement. No units are assigned to either cartesian axis. The graphics contained baseline data and that of the particular experiment itself. The direct observation of the resulting graphic was considered enough to see if any departure existed from the baseline.

3.4.2 | Basic and inferential statistics

Basic statistics were useful to make comparisons between data coming from baselines and actual experiments. Inferential statistics was used also to assess if there was a significant statistical difference between a baseline and an experimental set of data.

3.4.3 | Wavelet

Wavelet analysis is scale independent for the task of time-frequency localization, therefore it is useful for analyses where a predetermined scaling may not be appropriate because of a wide range of dominant frequencies [43]. The graphical result of this technique is a scalogram, which, when it is densely populated (precisely because of the existence of a wide range of frequencies), serves for identifying fractals.

A scalogram is a graphic result of applying a wavelet (in Mathematica 10, the default wave is MexicanHatWavelet, which is the second derivative of a Gaussian curve). A wavelet is a function which changes from zero up to a maximum, and then decreases to zero, symmetrically. This implies that the function's integral is zero. Upon applying a wavelet at different scales, the process may reveal a fractal structure, if there is any.

3.4.4 | Multifractal analysis

Let $D(Q)$ be a distortion of the mean (μ) of the probability distribution for a pattern [44, 45, 46].

Let $\alpha(Q)$ be the estimate of the slope of the regression line for $\log A_{\epsilon,Q}$ versus $\log \epsilon$, where

$$A_{\epsilon,Q} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\epsilon}} \mu_{i,\epsilon,Q} P_{i,\epsilon,Q} \quad (4)$$

Where $P_{i,\epsilon,Q}$ is the probability of a given mass relative to the total mass for a box size.

Finally let $f(\alpha)$ the fractal spectrum

$$f(\alpha) = D_F \{x, \alpha(x) = \alpha\} \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha(x)$ is the function describing the Hölder exponent, $\alpha(x)$ of $f(x)$ at the point x . $D_F \{\cdot\}$ is the Hausdorff dimension of a point set.

The graphic of $f(\alpha)$ vs α allows to give an idea of the extent of multifractality a given set of data has. Roughly speaking, the more the graphic resembles an wide open inverted "u", the more multifractal the data is, while a geometric circle will render a graphic close to a straight upward line [47].

4 | RESULTS

Because of the large volume of experiments and measurements made, only a selection of graphics is presented. The entire set of measurements, graphics and algorithmic procedures of Mathematica has been made available in the platform ResearchGate within a ResearchGate project (folder) with the same name as in this article (The Fractal Structure of Consciousness), under the name of the first author, i.e, at <https://www.researchgate.net/project/Gravitational-Anomalies-and-Shintergy-brain-synchronization>

4.1 | First Laser Experiments (2019)

The collection of the most representative graphics, from experiments made between October and December 2019 is shown. At this time, the described laser was the only operational measuring device.

4.1.1 | Yellow

This section exhibit the influence over a laser, in close proximity of space, and in the present time (Fig.5).

FIGURE 5 Thirteenth measurement, yellow condition, December 20.

4.1.2 | Red

In Present at a distance is where one begins to realize the non-locality, and the strong qualitative differences with the baselines (Figs.6).

FIGURE 6 Second measurement, Red condition, December 18th.

4.1.3 | Blue

Blue is intention of action at the future time, at a distance. Again, the qualitative differences between baselines and the Shintergy practice show that an interaction apparently exists (Figs.7, 8).

FIGURE 7 Fifth measurement, December 19th. Here was done while thinking on "death" in general.

FIGURE 8 Sixth measurement, Blue condition, December 19th. It is possible to notice that not necessarily brilliancy is lost; sometimes there is a *gain* in brilliancy, as it is the case.

4.1.4 | Green

In the green condition the Shintergy state is projected towards the past time (Figs.9, 10).

FIGURE 9 Second measurement, December 18th.

FIGURE 10 Sixth measurement, December 18th.

4.2 | Scale weight experiments, Kathmandu (January 2020)

The experiments consisted on setting a weight scale, either with weight or without. Again, the focus on the machine changed upon three different perspectives: Future, at a distance (blue); Past at a distance (Green), and Present time at a distance (Red). Kathmandu refers to the capital city of Nepal, from which each Shintergy synchronization was sent as an intention towards the machines, back in Mexico.

In these series of experiments, aside from the plotting of raw data, scalograms are also used.

It is argued that a weight scale with/without weight should mark a constant measure, whereas the existence of any deviation from such assumed inertia, per force indicates that something acts upon the weighting measurements, even after taking in account some initial bobbing effect of the springs in scale.

In the graphics, it is indicated “W” (with weight: 3 coins of 3.95 grams, which the machine should mark as 0.1 kg); “NW” (no weight). “↑”, meaning that, according to the basic statistics, weight went up, and “↓” that weight went down (Figs. 11, 12, 13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20).

Each experiment had a synchronization type as can be seen graphically in Fig.4. Such intention is reproduced before each graphic pair. The laser measurements correspond to each scale weigh measurement.

4.2.1 | Condition BLUE

FIGURE 11 First measurement, "NW". ↑

FIGURE 12 First measurement, "NW". ↑

FIGURE 13 Sixth measurement, "W". ↑

(a) laser raw data

(b) Scalogram of laser data.

FIGURE 14 Sixth measurement, "W". ↑

4.2.2 | Condition GREEN

FIGURE 15 Third measurement, "W". ↓

(a) laser raw data

(b) Scalogram of laser data.

FIGURE 16 Third measurement, "W". ↓

FIGURE 17 Fifth measurement, "W". ↑

FIGURE 18 Fifth measurement, "W". ↑

4.2.3 | Condition RED

FIGURE 19 Sixth measurement, "W". ↑

(a) laser raw data

(b) Scalogram of laser data.

FIGURE 20 Sixth measurement, "W". ↑

4.3 | Neurological and physical measurements simultaneously

These experiments attempted to substantiate a correlation between the access to the Shintergy synchronization according to the different time labels, identifiable through neurological measurements, and the physical measurements. The experiments were performed between March 11th through March 13th, 2020. In this set of experiments it was added the measurement of the time difference between two chronometers (Figs. 21,22,23), which is plotted for each type of time-intention experiment, and their corresponding fractal graphics. In Fig.25 and Fig.26 are shown the scalogram and multifractal graphics, respectively for Fig.24.

4.3.1 | Basal line

neurological measurements

Statistically significant changes are observed in the absolute power of:

- Decrease of power: T5 (-0.7) in Delta
- Increase of power: Fp2 (0.6) in Beta, Beta 3 and Hi-Beta; F8 (0.6) in Delta

4.3.2 | Red line

neurological measurements

Statistically significant changes are observed in the absolute power of:

- Decrease of power: O1 (-0.6) in Delta, T5 (-1.6) in Delta, O2 (-0.6) in Delta, T6 (-0.8) in Delta
- Increase of power: Fp2 (0.7) in Beta, Beta 3 and Hi-Beta

4.3.3 | Green line

neurological measurements

Statistically significant changes are observed in the absolute power of:

FIGURE 21 Chronometers difference, red condition, March 12th, 2020. Notice that instead of a whole straight region of uniformly distributed measurements, there is a marked shift of regions of time differences.

- Decrease of power: C3 (-0.6) in Delta, O1 (-0.9) in Delta, T5 (-1.6) in Delta, T6 (-0.8) in Delta, Pz (-0.6) in Alpha
- Increase of power: Fp2 (0.9) in Beta 3, Fp2 (0.8) in Hi-Beta, F8 (0.7) in Delta

FIGURE 22 Chronometers difference. Green condition, March 13th, 2020

4.3.4 | Blue line

neurological measurements

Statistically significant changes are observed in the absolute power of:

- Decrease of power: T5 (-1.5) in Delta
- Increase of power: Fp1 (0.6) in Beta, Beta-1 and Hi-Beta, Fp1 (0.7) in Beta 2, F3 (0.6) in Beta, F3 (0.8) in Beta 1, F3 (0.9) in Beta 2, C3 (0.6) in Theta, C3 (0.7) in Beta 1 and Beta 2, P3 (0.7) in Delta and Theta, P3 (0.8) in Beta, P3 (1.0) in Beta 1, P3 (1.2) in Beta 2, P3 (0.6) in Hi-Beta, O1 (0.6) in Theta, O1 (1.2) in Beta, O1 (1.3) in Beta 1, O1 (1.7) in Beta 2, O1 (0.9) in Beta 3, O1 (1.0) in Hi-Beta, F7 (0.6) in Beta, F7 (0.7) in Beta 1 and Beta 2, T3 (0.8) in Delta, Beta 3 and Hi-Beta, T3 (0.9) in Theta and Beta, T3 (0.7) in Alpha, T3 (1.0) in Beta 1, T3 (1.1) in Beta 2, T5 (0.7) in Alpha, T5 (0.6) in Beta, T5 (0.9) in Beta 1, T5 (1.0) in Beta 2, Fz (0.6) in Delta and Beta, Fz (0.8) in Beta 1, Fz (0.9) in Beta 2, F4 (0.7) in Beta 1 and Beta 2, C4 (0.6) in Beta 2, P4 (0.6) in Beta, P4 (0.7) in Beta 1, P4 (1.0) in Beta 2, O2 (0.8) in Beta, O2 (1.1) in Beta 1, O2 (1.3) in Beta 2, O2 (0.6) in Beta 3, O2 (0.7) in Hi-Beta, T6 (0.8) in Beta, T6 (1.0) in Beta 1, T6 (1.2) in Beta 2, Cz (0.7) in Delta and Beta 1, Cz (0.8) in Theta and Beta 2, Cz (0.6) in Beta, Cz (0.7) in Beta 1, Cz (0.8) in Beta 2, Pz (0.7) in Beta 1, Pz (1.0) in Beta 2.

FIGURE 23 Chronometers difference. Blue condition, March 11th 2020

4.3.5 | Yellow line

neurological measurements

Statistically significant changes are observed in the absolute power of:

- Decrease of power: O1 (-0.9) in Delta, T5 (-0.6) in Delta.
- Increase of power: Fp1 (0.7) in Gamma, F3 (0.6) in Gamma, C3 (0.6) in Beta 3 and Hi-Beta, C3 (0.9) in Gamma, P3

(0.6) in Gamma, O1 (0.6) in Gamma, F7 (0.6) in Gamma, T3 (0.6) in Beta 1 and Hi-Beta, T3 (0.9) in Gamma, Fz (0.6) in Gamma, F4 (0.7) en Gamma, C4 (0.8) in Gamma, P4 (0.6) in Gamma, O2 (0.6) in Gamma, T4 (0.6) in Gamma, Cz (0.7) in Gamma.

FIGURE 24 Chronometers difference. Yellow condition, March 12th, 2020

FIGURE 25 Scalogram, March 12th, 2020

FIGURE 26 $f(\alpha)$ vs α , March 12th, 2020

4.4 | Last Experiments

These experiments were performed between April 14th and April 17th, 2020. It is to be noticed that when the subject under Shintergy synchronization tried to focus the intent over modifying reality, there was an apparent coincidence in time when several parts of the equipment stopped working, and plainly broke (April 17th). Here it is shown only the most relevant events, occurred on April 16th (Fig.27) and April 17th (Fig.28).

4.4.1 | Chronometers, April 16th

FIGURE 27 Chronometers difference. Baseline. This is the only measurement when chronometers behaved as expected: with a uniform distribution

4.4.2 | Chronometers, April 17th

FIGURE 28 Chronometers difference. Blue condition.

5 | DISCUSSION

5.1 | General remarks

The graphics of raw data clearly show a deviation from a baseline. In the case of laser light, the behavior is non-optical, since in some instances the brilliancy decreases, but in others *increase*, and similar observations go for the case of the weight scale, and the chronometers, which sometimes follow a relativistic behavior, and in some cases exotic gravitational effects appear.

The change in brilliancy of the laser, as it was implied, at the beginning was considered to be of optical nature, but when the weight scale and the chronometers were set-up, it was assumed that the change of brilliancy is due to gravitational, relativistic effects, possibly due to the presence of a singularity, in agreement to the fractal model of consciousness.

Most scalograms indeed show fractal behavior, and the time differences between chronometers show what would be expected in general relativity, when a chronometer approach an event horizon. Some of the time differences (like the red condition here included) show a behavior which is not entirely consistent with general relativity, because of the abrupt change, as opposite to a continuous time-shift.

Although it is apparent that the usage of Shintergy synchronization has a close correlation to these phenomena, even having the neurological evidence, there is no detailed mechanical explanation on how it occurs, nor how it can be finely-tuned on its control, if it is possible a control at all; this is mentioned, because as it was mentioned before, the Shintergy synchronization does require an abandonment of an intention of control.

5.2 | Neurological measurements

In this section it is discussed the neurological meaning of the electrode measurements.

5.2.1 | Red condition (present at a distance)

The decrease in Delta potency is concentrated in the left occipital region (AB 18, 19), which could be associated with a decrease in visuo-perceptual processing.

The increase in Gamma potency is concentrated in the left prefrontal region (AB 9, 10), which could be associated with attentional control, self-awareness, modulation and inhibition of impulses.

5.2.2 | Green condition (past at a distance)

The decrease in Delta potency is concentrated in the right prefrontal region (AB 10, 11), which could be associated with inhibition of behavior. The increase in Gamma potency is bilaterally concentrated in the frontal region (AB 8, 9, 10, 11, 46, Fig.29), which could be associated with self-monitoring, empathy, control of attention, sustained attention, self-awareness, modulation and inhibition of impulses and behavior.

FIGURE 29 Default Mode Network of the brain while in the Shintergy synchronization (Green condition, past at a distance). The color scale in the brain image, correspond to standard deviations referred at the left of the figure. It is worth noticing that, as it is mentioned in the text, only the frontal region is shown, and not the whole network.

5.2.3 | Blue condition (future at a distance)

Increased Hi-Beta potency is concentrated in the left inferior frontal gyrus (AB 44, 45, 46) and temporal pole (AB 38), which could be associated with internal language, positive emotions, emotional attachment and evocation of memories. The decrease in Delta power is concentrated in the left and right parietal, occipital, and temporal lobes, which could be associated with a decrease in multimodal sensory information processing (auditory, visual, somesthetic).

5.2.4 | Yellow condition (present time, 5 meters apart from devices)

The decrease in the power of Delta is concentrated in the upper right parietal region (AB 7, 5), which could be associated with the decrease in visuospatial processing, with the perception of personal space and the sensation of "I".

The increase in Delta power is bilaterally concentrated in the prefrontal region (AB 10), which could be associated with modulation and inhibition of impulses and behavior.

The increase in Gamma power is mainly concentrated in the upper left parietal region (AB 7, 5) and the left motor and premotor region (AB 4, 8), which could be associated with visuospatial processing, the perception of space personal and the feeling of "I", self-monitoring and imagination of movement.

5.3 | Apparent relationship of consciousness with dark matter

The time-region shift in Fig.(4.3.2) was used in the formula

$$t_0 = t_f \sqrt{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \quad (6)$$

taking $t_0 = 128s$, $t_f = 128.5s$, G is the gravitational constant, $r = 3m$ (roughly radius size of the space where the equipment was) and c the speed of light, it was solved for M to obtain

$$M = 1.6 \times 10^{25} [\text{kg}] \quad (7)$$

Using this result on the Schwarzschild radius

$$r_s = \frac{2M}{c^2} = 0.023 [\text{m}] \quad (8)$$

The volume of the singularity would be at most

$$V = \frac{3}{4}\pi r_s^3 \approx 2.86678 \times 10^{-5} [\text{m}^3] \quad (9)$$

Now, let $m_l = 2.18 \times 10^{-8}$ [Kg] be the Planck mass [28], since it is used in [28] as a fundamental measure to solve the vacuum catastrophe, thus solving the problem of dark energy and matter. So,

$$n = \frac{M}{m_l} = \frac{1.6 \times 10^{25}}{2.18 \times 10^{-8}} = 7.33945 \times 10^{32} \quad (10)$$

Now, it is known that quantum effects appear if [48]

$$\frac{N}{V} \geq n_q \quad (11)$$

where n_q is the quantum concentration defined as [49, 48]

$$n_q = 2.612 \left(\frac{2\pi M k T}{h^2} \right)^{3/2}$$

when $T = T_B$, T_B being the Bose temperature for the Bose-Einstein statistics [48], then an increasing number of bosons may occupy the ground state, as $T < T_B$ until all bosons, regardless of number, occupy the same ground state [48]. Taking the results of Eq.9 and Eq.10, our quantum concentration is

$$\frac{7.33945 \times 10^{32}}{2.86678 \times 10^{-5} [\text{m}^3]} = 2.56017 \times 10^{37} [\text{m}^{-3}] \quad (12)$$

Even taking the original volume of the experimental set up as

$$V_{exp} = (3/4)\pi * 3^3 = 63.6173 [\text{m}^3] \quad (13)$$

it is obtained

$$\frac{7.33945 \times 10^{32}}{63.6173 [\text{m}^3]} = 1.15369 \times 10^{31} [\text{m}^{-3}] = 11.5369 \approx 12 [\text{\AA}^{-3}] \quad (14)$$

For comparison, the quantum number n_q for protons is in the scale of $1 [\text{\AA}^{-3}]$ (one proton per cubic Angstrom) [48], and it could be thought that asymptotically (as per the Law of large Numbers [50]) the result of Eq.14 should converge to

$$n_q \sim 10 [\text{\AA}^{-3}], \quad (15)$$

which presumably would account for the 100% of energy and mass of the volume, as per the definition of how matter, energy and dark matter and dark energy are distributed in the universe [28].

Granted, the experimental conditions (room temperature, and sea level atmospheric pressure), do not warrant by any means anything like the conditions required for a Bose-Einstein condensate. However, the definition of consciousness as a fractal capable of inducing gravitational singularities, the close correspondence of a Bose-Einstein condensate to a structure without a defined scale (like fractals), and some of the observational results for dark matter and the results of Eq.7, do seem to have a possible connection, even though the evidence points to physics that still

needs to be explored.

Since the Planck mass was taken as a unit for solving the problem of gravitational singularities, and, by the free-will-theorem [5], it follows that the Planck mass could be taken as a particle. In the conjecture described in 1, the *quantum of consciousness*.

Moreover, since the canonical partition of a Bose-Einstein condensate can be defined with recursive functions [51], and since recursivity is a necessary and sufficient condition for a fractal to exist [14], it follows the congruence with conjecture 1.

6 | CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

Shintergy synchronization seems in close correlation to the observed phenomena, although no mechanical, detailed explanation (cause-effect) can be offered.

The post-processing of data did indeed show fractal behavior, hence it is concluded that the measurements do have fractal behavior, consistent with the conjecture that consciousness has fractal structure, as per the definition; furthermore, the gravitational anomalies results are consistent with a percolating network of multifractal, which in turn are consistent with the theorized consciousness field that induces a gravitational singularity, and which is described by Planck particles. It is thus concluded that the features of a Planck mass particle (presumably the Planck particle or PSU from [52] identify it as a quantum of consciousness, and by the relationship with the features with a Bose-Einstein condensate recursive partition, it is a fractal, as per the here in stated conjecture.

The time differences exhibit some clustering that may be studied topologically in future research, which could render further information about more structure in the distribution of measurements than is apparent.

Multifractality evidence suggest that indeed there may be a percolating network, and hence a hierarchy of consciousness, which should be explored in the future.

Future exploration concerning the stability of the Shintergy state of synchronization should be considered.

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Supporting Information

As it was mentioned, further supporting information can be found at the following page <https://www.researchgate.net/project/Gravitational-Anomalies-and-Shintergy-brain-synchronization>

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